

Reactivity of Conjugated Systems. Part IV.
Condensation of Alkylidene Ketones
with Cyanoacetamide.

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In previous communications of this series (Barat, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 321; 1931, 8, 37), it has been shown that in a conjugated system of the type $R\cdot CH=CH\cdot X$, the reactivity of the ethylenic linkage towards additive reactions with regard to reactive methylene groups is governed to a considerable extent by the nature of the negative character of the group X, which consists of a so-called negative grouping containing a carbonyl group in conjugation with the ethylenic, and follows the three-carbon system rule of Lapworth and McRae (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 2747), and also of Kon and his collaborators (*ibid.*, 1923, 125, 1361; and subsequent papers). In other words it has been fully substantiated there by keeping R constant and varying the nature of the substituent X, that the reactivity of this ethylenic bond is enhanced by an increase in the negative character of X, and *vice versa*. Thus the order of the yields or the condensation products as well as their ease of formation follow the order:

In the present work R has been changed from the aryl group Ph into the alkyl group Me, and it has been found that the activity is appreciably enhanced, subject, however, to the nature of the substituent X. This difference might of course be due to two causes, *viz.*, (1) the less negative nature of the methyl group than phenyl, or, (2) the smaller volume occupied by the former than the latter—thus offering less steric obstruction to the primary additive reaction, which, necessarily precedes the subsequent ring-closure by the elimination of water.

From the evidence in hand, this latter cause seems to be more reasonable, as by taking mesityl oxide, where there are two methyl

pounds which were described by the present author as closed ring keto-lactols on the ground that they are soluble in sodium bicarbonate solution, in a finely ground condition and as such must contain free carboxyl groups. On careful repetition of the previous experiments it has now been found that these substances dissolve very slowly in cold bicarbonate solution, but the rate of dissolution does not indicate a free carboxyl group at any rate; further the formation of an unsaturated lactone (VI), by treatment with acetyl chloride or acetic anhydride, strongly indicates the probability of at least a momentary existence of the lactol form (V), since the formation of (VI) cannot be explained from an open-chain ketonic structure (IV) (*cf.* Vorländer and Knotzsch, *Annalen*, 1897, 294, 333).

It must be observed, however, that between a "fixed keto-lactol configuration" and a "no keto-lactol configuration" there may be intermediate stages (depending upon the nature and volume of substituents and other probable considerations) where some sort of a loose keto-lactol phase may exist. The existence of an equilibrium between the keto-acid and the keto-lactol is not unlikely in these cases as in many instances where an aldol form is possible it has usually been isolated. (*cf.* the case of hydroxypiperidine derivatives (VII) described herein, as well as the case of *pseudo*-urethanes, Sen and Barat, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 3, 405). It is evident nevertheless, that the constitution of these compounds cannot be fully cleared up without physico-chemical experiments. This will be taken up as soon as time and opportunity permit. Till then these compounds have been provisionally described as open-chain δ -ketonic acids.

The products obtained by Knoevenagel's reaction consist of the hydroxypiperidine derivatives (VII) which are readily converted into the Michael compounds (I) upon dehydration, and give upon hydrolysis the same δ -ketonic acids as afforded by the corresponding Michael compounds.

These tetrahydropyridones can be converted into the corresponding dihydro-derivatives by means of nitrous acid or bromine. The latter when hydrolysed by 75 p.c. sulphuric acid in the usual way give the hydroxypyridines (VIII) characterised by their colour reactions with ferric chloride.

Mesityl oxide behaves differently from these ethylidene ketones by giving the hydroxypiperidine derivative (analogous to VII,) even with sodium ethoxide; such that identical compounds are obtained both by Michael's and Knoevenagel's reactions. The aldol phase, however, is easily removable when dehydrated in the usual way. The most interesting feature of this compound is its failure to give rise to a dihydro-derivative with nitrous acid or bromine, which confirms the statement made in Part I of this series that it is the 4 and 5 carbon atoms of these tetrahydropyridones that are removed during dehydrogenation, and corroborates the constitution ascribed to these bodies in that paper. This stability towards dehydrogenating agents is doubtlessly due to there being no hydrogen atom attached to the carbon atom 4, without the help of which no dehydrogenation is possible. Tetrahydroacetophenone, $\text{CH}_3 \cdot \text{CO} \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_9$, on the other hand, gives the octahydro-*isoquinoline* derivative (IX), with cyanoacetamide both by Michael's as well as Knoevenagel's reactions. Further, it is readily hydrolysed into the corresponding hydroxy-compound (X), without rupture of either of the fused rings, thus showing the stabler nature of partially reduced quinoline rings as compared with the corresponding pyridine rings.

The hydroxy-compound (X) on successive distillation with zinc dust and litharge gives rise to 1-*methyl-isoquinoline* (XI), identified by means of its picrate and platinichloride. This provides with an absolutely new method of *isoquinoline* synthesis.

With malonic ester this ketone gives rise to a dihydroxy-hexahydronaphthalene derivative (XII), after the fashion of the formation of dihydroresorcinol derivatives from benzylidene acetone and malonic ester, first recorded by Vorländer (*Annalen*, 1897, 294, 273).

EXPERIMENTAL.

General Method.—The condensations were carried out with cyanoacetamide both by Michael's and Knoevenagel's reactions as described in the case of arylidene ketones. Only in the present cases the reaction products were not allowed to remain in the reacting (alkaline) medium for any greater length of time than was necessary for the completion of the condensation reaction in order to prevent the formation of the dihydro-derivatives. The small quantity of this latter product that was inevitably formed, specially by the Michael's reaction, was easily separated by digesting the whole reaction product with rectified spirits, in which it was almost insoluble. From the portion soluble in alcohol, the tetrahydro-compound was obtained in a pure state after two or three crystallisations from alcohol till the melting point became constant and sharp. The piperidine reaction product was obtained sufficiently pure when the reaction mixture was worked up within two to three days. Longer duration gave appreciable quantities of the dihydropyridone. Both the condensation products when hydrolysed by concentrated hydrochloric acid in a sealed tube in the usual way, gave the same open-chain acid, which could also be obtained from the reaction product of the corresponding ketone and malonic ester by Michael's method. The Michael product was dehydrogenated as usual by nitrous acid in acetic acid solution, and hydrolysed into the corresponding hydroxypyridine by means of 75 p. c. sulphuric acid in the way described before.

I. *Condensation of Ethylidene Acetophenone
with Cyanoacetamide.*

The ketone was prepared by the method of Kohler (*Amer. Chem. J.*, 1909, 42, 375) from crotonic acid through the intermediary of the bromo-ketone, as direct condensation of crotonyl chloride with benzene by Friedel-Craft's reaction gave a very low yield of the desired product and more of β -phenylbutyrophenone, $\text{Ph}\cdot\text{CH}\cdot(\text{CH}_3)\cdot\text{CH}_2\cdot\text{CO}\cdot\text{Ph}$. The bromo-ketone was debrominated by alcoholic

potassium iodide as this gave a more satisfactory yield than by its reduction with zinc

Michael's Reaction: (I, R=Ph) *Formation of 2-keto-3-cyano-4-methyl-6-phenyl-2:3:4:5-tetrahydropyridine*.—The total condensation product obtained by diluting and acidulating the reaction mixture after two days came to about 90 p. c. of theory, of which about 10 p. c. consisted of the dehydrogenated product, which was left behind when the whole mass was extracted with rectified spirits. The tetrahydropyridone was obtained from the alcohol solution and after three crystallisations from alcohol melted at 248-50°. It had all the properties of its other homologues described previously. (Found: N, 13.51. $C_{13}H_{12}ON_2$ requires N, 13.2 per cent.).

Knoevenagel's Reaction: (VII, R=Ph) *Formation of 2-keto-3-cyano-4-methyl-6-phenyl-6-hydroxypiperidine*.—This compound also was obtained in a very good yield after three days, and was isolated by acidulating the reaction mixture with dilute mineral acids. Crystallised from alcohol it was obtained in fine short needles, m. p. 177-78°. It could be readily dehydrated by gaseous hydrogen chloride in chloroform or carbon tetrachloride suspension in the usual way. (Found: N, 12.43. $C_{13}H_{14}O_2N_2$ requires N, 12.17 per cent.).

Hydrolysis of the Condensation Products: Formation of β -Methyl- γ -benzoylbutyric Acid.—This could be easily obtained by hydrolysing any of the above condensation products with concentrated hydrochloric acid in a sealed tube at 120-25° for 3-4 hours. It separated as an oil, which when extracted with ether, dried and evaporated, did not readily solidify, but did so on being left in vacuum over sulphuric acid. Crystallised from a mixture of chloroform and petroleum ether it melted at 72-73°. It was extremely soluble in all solvents excepting petroleum ether and resembled its other homologues in its other properties. (Found: C, 70.05; H, 7.20; M.W. (by titration), 207.5. $C_{12}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 69.9; H, 6.8 per cent., M.W., 206).

Formation of 3-cyano-4-methyl-6-phenyl-2-pyridone(II, R=Ph).—Apart from the spontaneous formation of this compound, by the Michael's reaction referred to above, it could be easily prepared by treating the tetrahydropyridone with nitrous acid in the usual way. Crystallised from glacial acetic acid or pyridine it was obtained in beautiful cream coloured prisms, that melted at 309-10°, and was identical with a specimen prepared by Basu (*J. Indian Chem.Soc.*, 1930, 7, 488). (Found: N, 13.26. $C_{13}H_{10}ON_2$ requires N, 13.33 per cent.).

Hydrolysis of above : Formation of 2-hydroxy-4-methyl-6-phenylpyridine (VIII, R=Ph).— This was obtained by heating the above compound with 75 p. c. sulphuric acid till the liberation of carbon dioxide ceased. The hydroxypyridine did not separate on cooling and diluting the acid solution but was obtained on neutralising the same by sodium carbonate. It was extremely soluble in all solvents, insoluble in petroleum ether and cold water, but moderately so in boiling water. Crystallised from 40 per cent. alcohol (charcoal) it was obtained in fine white needles, m.p. 180-81°. It was compared with a specimen from stock, (Basu, *loc.cit.*). It gave a beautiful violet coloration with ferric chloride, and possessed the other properties ascribed to this type of compounds in previous publications. (Found: N, 7.92. $C_{12}H_{11}ON$ requires N, 7.57 per cent.).

Condensation with Malonic Ester : Formation of α -carboxy- β -methyl- γ -benzoylbutyric Acid, and the action of heat on it.— The condensation was carried out as usual and the product was directly hydrolysed by dilute potassium hydroxide. The acid that separated as an oil on acidulation was extracted with ether followed by the usual treatments. It was very soluble in all solvents and crystallised from a mixture of chloroform and petroleum ether, m.p. 141-42° (decomp.) and resembled its other homologues in its properties. (Found: C, 62.15; H, 5.85; M.W. (by titration), 253. $C_{13}H_{14}O_5$ requires C, 62.4; H, 5.6 per cent., M.W., 250). On being heated at its melting point till effervescence ceased, it was converted into the monobasic keto-acid described above.

II. *Condensation of Ethylidene-p-Methylacetophenone with Cyanoacetamide.*

The ketone was obtained in an exactly similar way as in the previous case, by substituting benzene with toluene in the Friedel-Craft's reaction. α : β -*i*Dibromo-*p*-methylbutyrophenone, $CH_3 \cdot CHBr \cdot CH \cdot Br \cdot CO \cdot C_6H_4 \cdot CH_3$ was prepared now for the first time and was found to resemble its lower homologue in all its properties. Crystallised from dilute alcohol it was obtained in fine white needles, m. p. 120-21°. (Found: Br, 49.65. $C_{11}H_{12}OBr_2$ requires Br, 50.0 per cent.). It was debrominated as in the previous case by alcoholic iodide and resembled its lower homologue in its properties. It was a pale yellow oil that boiled at 222°/16 mm.

The condensations with cyanoacetamide and malonic ester were carried out in an exactly similar manner as in the previous case and

so the condensation products alone have been described here, the experimental details being omitted.

2-Keto-3-cyano-4-methyl-6-p-tolyl-2:3:4:5-tetrahydropyridine (I, R=*p*-tolyl) was obtained in an yield similar to the previous case, mixed with a small quantity of the dihydro-compound, and was separated by treating with alcohol as before. After three crystallisations from alcohol it melted at 255-56°. (Found: N, 12.53. $C_{14}H_{14}ON_2$ requires N, 12.39 per cent.).

2-Keto-3-cyano-4-methyl-6-p-tolyl-6-hydroxypiperidine (VII, R=*p*-tolyl) was obtained by Knoevenagel's method and was isolated after three days. Crystallised from alcohol it melted at 163-64°. It could be readily converted into the Michael compound by dehydration in the usual way. (Found: N, 11.78. $C_{14}H_{16}O_2N_2$ requires N, 11.48 per cent.).

3-Cyano-4-methyl-6-p-tolyl-2-pyridone (II, R=*p*-tolyl) was prepared by treating the tetrahydropyridone with nitrous acid. Crystallised from glacial acetic acid or pyridine it was obtained in white prismatic plates, m. p. 330°, and was identical with a specimen obtained from *p*-toluoylacetone and cyanoacetamide by Basu (*J. Indian Chem.Soc.*, 1931, 8, 124). (Found: N, 12.86. $C_{14}H_{12}ON_2$ requires N, 12.5 per cent.).

2-Hydroxy-4-methyl-6-p-tolylpyridine (VIII, R=*p*-tolyl) was obtained by hydrolysing the above by 75 p. c. sulphuric acid and isolated as in the previous case. Crystallised from dilute alcohol it melted at 183°, and was identical with the specimen described by Basu (*loc.cit.*, *supra*). It gave a violet coloration with ferric chloride. (Found: N, 7.21. $C_{13}H_{13}ON$ requires N, 7.04 per cent.)

*α -Carboxy- β -methyl- γ -*p*-toluoylbutyric acid* was obtained by hydrolysing the condensation product between the unsaturated ketone and malonic ester by aqueous potassium hydroxide. Crystallised from a mixture of petroleum ether and chloroform it melted at 125°, (decomp). [Found: C, 63.51; H, 6.32; M.W. (by titration) 262.8. $C_{14}H_{16}O_5$ requires C, 63.64; H, 6.06 per cent., M.W., 264].

*β -Methyl- γ -*p*-toluoylbutyric acid* was obtained by heating the above at its melting point for sometime, as well as by hydrolysing any of the original cyanoacetamide condensation products by concentrated hydrochloric acid as in the former case. It solidified on cooling and crystallised from hot water in long colourless needles, m.p. 105.6°. [Found: C, 75.68; H, 7.51; M.W. (by titration), 218.2. $C_{13}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 75.45; H, 7.27 per cent. M.W., 220].

III. *Condensation of Ethylidene Acetone with Cyanoacetamide.*

The unsaturated ketone was prepared from hydracetylacetone [pentanol-(4)-one-(2)-], obtained by condensing acetaldehyde with acetone in presence of potassium cyanide according to the method of Claisen and others, (*Annalen*, 1899, 306, 322) by dehydration with anhydrous oxalic acid after Pauli and Berg (*Ber.*, 1901 34, 2092) as this method gave a better yield than the previously known ones.

2-Keto-3-cyano-4:6-dimethyl-2:3:4:5-tetrahydropyridine (I, R=Me) was obtained in a good yield when the above ketone was condensed with cyanoacetamide in the usual way by Michael's reaction. The product being very sparingly soluble in all solvents, it was best purified by dissolving in alkali followed by precipitation with dilute mineral acids. It was thereby obtained as a white granular powder, which had no m.p. but sublimed away on being heated. (Found: N, 18.58. $C_8H_{10}ON_2$ requires N, 18.67 per cent.).

2-Keto-3-cyano-4:6-dimethyl-6-hydroxypiperidine (VII, R=Me) was obtained also in a good yield when the two substances were condensed in presence of piperidine. The substance was isolated as usual and crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 173-75°. (Found: N, 16.85. $C_8H_{12}O_2N_2$ requires N, 16.67 per cent.).

3-Cyano-4:6-dimethyl-2-pyridone (II, R=Me) was prepared from the above tetrahydropyridine derivatives by dehydrogenation with nitrous acid in the usual way. It was identified with an identical product obtained by condensing acetylacetone with cyanoacetamide (Basu, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 7, 490). Crystallised from dilute acetic acid it melted at 289°. (*cf.* Guareschi, *Atti. R. Accad. Sci. Torino*, 1893, 28, 330, 8370). (Found: N, 19.04, $C_8H_8ON_2$ requires N, 18.92 per cent.).

IV. *Condensation of Mesityl Oxide with Cyanoacetamide.*

Mesityl oxide was prepared from diacetone alcohol, prepared by the self condensation of acetone in presence of barium hydroxide by the method of Conant and Tuttle, "Organic Synthesis", vol. I. p. 45, 53). The condensations were carried out in the usual manner, with the only exception that on account of the solubility of the products in water, they were obtained by evaporating the acidulated reaction

mixtures on the water-bath followed by extraction of the condensation products by alcohol. As has been mentioned in the theoretical part, the same hydroxypiperidine derivative, *2-keto-3-cyano-4:4:6-trimethyl-6-hydroxypiperidine* was obtained both by Michael's as well as by Knoevenagel's reactions. Crystallised from water or or alcohol it was obtained in colourless prisms, m.p. 273-75°. (Found: C, 59.64; H, 7.99; N,* 18.4. $C_9H_{14}O_2N_2$ requires C, 59.33; H, 7.69; N, 15.38 per cent.).

On treating the above compound with gaseous hydrochloric acid in carbon tetrachloride suspension, in the manner described previously, the dehydrated product, *2-keto-3-cyano-4:4:6-trimethyl-2:3:4:5-tetrahydropyridine* was obtained. On crystallisation from alcohol it melted at 252-54°. (Found: C, 65.53; H, 7.51. $C_9H_{12}ON_2$ requires C, 65.85; H, 7.31 per cent.). On treatment with nitrous acid both the above compounds were recovered unchanged, showing the stability of this substance towards oxidising agents. (cf. Qudrat-i-Khuda, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, p. 201).

V. Condensation of Tetrahydroacetophenone with Cyanoacetamide.

The ketone was prepared by Darzen's method (*Compt. rend.*, 1910, 150, 707) by condensing acetyl chloride with *cyclohexene* in presence of anhydrous stannic chloride. It was observed that the ketone could be better purified by steam distillation followed by distillation in vacuum, b.p. 95-100°/15-20 mm. *cyclohexene* was prepared by the method of Coleman and Johnstone from *cyclohexanol* ('Organic Synthesis', vol. V. p. 33).

In this case also the reactions (both Michael and Knoevenagel) characterised themselves by yielding the same octahydro *isoquinolone* derivatives by both reactions. Further, this compound is easily hydrolysed into the corresponding hydroxy-compound by 75 p. c. sulphuric acid without rupture of any of the two fused rings and yields a methyl derivative quite readily by means of dimethyl sulphate.

Formation of *1-methyl-3-keto-4-cyano-3:4:5:6:7:8:9:10-octahydro-isoquinoline* (IX).—This compound was obtained in an yield

* The high nitrogen figure in the analytical data, is due to the presence of a little methane that invariably comes with the nitrogen when such hydroaromatic bases containing two methyl groups attached to any one carbon atom is combusted with cupric oxide in the ordinary way (Haas, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1906, 89, 570).

of about 60 p. c. by Michael's reaction and about 50 p. c. by Kneovenagel's reaction. It was nearly insoluble in all solvents excepting glacial acetic acid and pyridine. It resembled the dihydro-pyridones in all its properties, and crystallised from pyridine in fine white short needles, m.p. 358-60°. (Found: N, 14.97. $C_{11}H_{14}ON_2$ requires N, 14.74 per cent.).

Hydrolysis of the above: Formation of the Compound (X).—The hydrolysis was carried out with 75 p. c. sulphuric acid in the usual way when the hydroxy-compound could be obtained by neutralising the diluted solution with sodium carbonate. Crystallised from dilute alcohol it was obtained in fine white felty needles, m. p. 231-32° (decomp.). It dissolved in alkalis quite readily and was precipitated unchanged on acidulation, and gave a reddish-violet coloration with ferric chloride. (Found: N, 8.53. $C_{10}H_{15}ON$ requires N, 8.48 per cent.).

The *N-methyl ether* of the original condensation product (IX) was prepared by dissolving it in aqueous alkali and adding an excess of dimethyl sulphate little by little with good shaking, and keeping the solution alkaline by the addition of alkali from time to time. The mixture warmed up during the operation and soon the methyl derivatives, being no longer soluble in alkali, began to separate, and was fully separated on cooling. It was filtered off, washed till free from alkali and crystallised from dilute alcohol when it was obtained in white felty needles, m. p. 122-23°. (Found: N, 14.03. $C_{12}H_{16}ON_2$ requires N, 13.72 per cent.).

Formation of 1-Methyl-isoquinoline (XI).—The hydroxy-compound (X) when distilled successively with zinc dust and litharge yields a heavy boiling basic oil. This was purified by extracting non-basic impurities with ether from its acid solution. It was reprecipitated with alkali, extracted with ether, and the free base isolated therefrom; it was a yellow oil with a characteristic quinolinous odour. Its ethereal solution when heated with a similar solution of picric acid yielded a *picrate* that crystallised from alcohol in fine yellow needles, m.p. 209-10°. [Found: N, 15.26. $C_{10}H_9N, C_6H_2(NO_2)_3 OH$ requires N, 15.06 per cent.].

The *platinichloride* obtained as usual melted at 200-202° (decomp.). [Found: Pt, 27.86. $(C_{10}H_9N, HCl)_2 PtCl_4$ requires Pt, 28.02. per cent.].

Condensation with Malonic Ester: Formation of 1:3-dihydroxy-5:6:7:8:9:10-hexahydronaphthalene (XII).—The condensation

was carried out as usual and the condensation product directly hydrolysed by boiling with dilute aqueous potash, on cooling, the solution was washed with ether and the hydrolysed product precipitated by acidulating the aqueous solution. It first separated as an oil which finally solidified, and was crystallised from dilute alcohol in white, short, prismatic needles, m.p. 115°. (Found: C, 71.35 ; H, 9.74. $C_{10}H_{16}O_2$ requires C, 71.43 ; H, 9.52 per cent.).

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